

of 189 positive samples in 11 different host species have been found in different foci in Mallorca (124), Menorca (16) and Ibiza (49) islands. Sequence analysis of the RNA polymerase sigma 70 factor sequence and MLST typing revealed the presence of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa* ST1 and *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* ST6* (a new ST with the closest being ST6) and ST7 in Mallorca island, *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* ST6* in Menorca island and *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* ST80 (a new ST) in Ibiza island. *Polygala myrtifolia* was found to be infected by all subspecies and ST types. Altogether, these results suggest that the emergence of *X. fastidiosa* in Balearic Islands is likely due to several introduction events of diverse strains from different subspecies. Eradication measures were taken in the garden center according to the Spanish contingency plan and EU legislation. Following the Commission Decision 2015/789/EU of establishing a radius of 10 km to delimit the buffer zone for each infected foci 80%, 50% and 90% of the territory of Mallorca, Menorca and Ibiza islands, respectively, are considered as demarcated areas. Consequently, the best strategy to control the different outbreaks is under study.

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***Xylella fastidiosa* in France: current situation in Corsica and in the region of Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur.**

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Abstract: Since the first outbreak of *X. fastidiosa* on *Polygala myrtifolia* (*Pm*) in natural settings in 2015 in France, the national survey showed that disease is present in many ornamental host plant in environment of Corsica and French Riviera (PACA). *X. fastidiosa* has been detected on around forty plant species with a validated method based on Real-Time PCR (Harper *et al.*, 2010) associated to DNA extraction with QuickPick™ Plant DNA kit (Bio-Nobile) and KingFisher™ automate (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The sample preparation and isolation performed on modified PWG medium (EPPO, 2016) have been optimized and more than 40 *X. fastidiosa* strains were isolated from various ornamentals and trees. The characterization of isolates directly on plant or on pure strains is performed according to a multilocus sequence typing (MLST) (http://pubmlst.org/X_fastidiosa/). Following EPPO protocol PM 7/24 isolates were mostly allocated to sequence types ST6 and ST7 (subspecies *multiplex*). Modifications of the amplification protocol (Yuan *et al.*, 2010) proposed by Denancé *et al.* (2017) revealed infections linked to the subspecies *pauca*, *sandyi*, one recombinant and some mixed infections. EPPO protocol MLST confirmed four isolates in *Polygala myrtifolia* from PACA contaminated with subsp. *pauca* but not the identification of other contaminants. These contaminations could not be observed again in the immediate environment after plant eradication. Subspecies assignment directly from plant material is not always successful linked to PCR inhibitors depending of host plants. This study confirms the diversity of subspecies of *X. fastidiosa* in France. Nevertheless subspecies *multiplex* was found in the great majority.

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***Xylella fastidiosa* in Costa Rica: understanding of the pathogen and containment through collaborative approach**

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Abstract: *X. fastidiosa* is endemic in Costa Rica. Since the 1990's, the appearance of a milder version of CLS was reported as "crespera" in Costa Rica. It was confirmed that the disease was due to *X. fastidiosa* infection. Since then, the bacterium has been detected and isolated from more than 20 different economic important crops and ornamentals. Although the bacterium has great potential for disease and it is widespread throughout the country, the symptoms related to infected plants are usually mild or asymptomatic. In 2015, the European Union closed the importation of ornamentals from Costa Rica, alleging that *X. fastidiosa* was introduced in this matter into Europe, causing great social and economic impact in this activity in Costa Rica. Recently, genomic evidence supports the relatedness of the CoDiRo strains to *X. fastidiosa* ST53 isolates from Costa Rica. Our participation as part of the PonTE and XFactors research efforts are focused on broadening the genetic and phenotypic information related to our circulating strains, this will contribute to dilucidate some specific traits of the *X. fastidiosa* strains found in Italy as in other European countries as well. We are also working on alternative containment strategies for the bacteria. Finally, we have established research initiatives related to endusers in collaboration with phytosanitary authorities to determine the host susceptibility to *X. fastidiosa* of economic important plants such as *Phoenix roebelenii*.

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Session 2 - *Xylella fastidiosa*: biology and genetics

Calcium has multiple roles during the interactions between *Xylella fastidiosa* and host plants

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Abstract: Inside the plant host *X. fastidiosa* is restricted to live inside xylem vessels, the vascular system where mineral elements are transported from the roots to the rest of the plant. Previous research by our group has demonstrated that calcium (Ca) increases movement and biofilm formation of *X. fastidiosa* by manipulating protein secondary structure and regulating gene expression. Interestingly, plants infected with *X. fastidiosa* also show accumulation of Ca in their leaves and xylem